

ROLE OF STRATEGIC PLANNING IN EFFICIENCY OF LOGISTICS SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The statistical population of the study consisted of 29 dairy companies, of which 25 samples were selected and based on a researcher-made questionnaire. It has been used to measure business strategy. Based on the results of the table, $R^2 = 0.76$, showed that the alignment with the business strategy with 95% confidence can significantly explain the variance of performance evaluation and performance measurement of the chains Supply. The alignment with business strategy affects performance evaluation and performance measurement of supply chains, and positive beta score indicates a positive relationship between these two components.

Keywords: Logistics Systems, Strategic Planning, supply efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Senior managers' responses to the restrictions and opportunities they face are referred to as strategy (.Miles & Snow,1978). Reactors are businesses that lack a well-defined strategy and react as a result of external factors (Hajar,2015). In later investigations, the hypothesised dimensions were tested and the approach kinds were empirically assessed (Blumentritt and Danis, 2006; Oltra and Flor, 2010). emphasise Miles and Snow's (1978) typology's stronger generalisability, applicability to low-concentrated industries established by small and medium-sized businesses, and the higher level of specification employed to define the types. Studies on the impact of strategic direction on creativity and performance, in particular, have shown increasingly clear evidence of favourable outcomes. As a result, utilising three strategic types, the following indicators were used to measure the company strategy: prospector, analyst, and defender.

The current study considers corporate strategy to be a competitive notion, and it is based on Venkatramen's comparative method, which he introduced in 1989. In the company strategy measuring instrument, he established six dimensions for strategic orientation:

The term "offensive strategy" refers to a company's strategic orientation that, in comparison to its competitors, quickly deploys resources to increase market position. This strategy orientation necessitates significant investment as well as a contribution to market development.

Analytical Strategy is a broad approach to problem resolution that combines strategic decisions with an in-depth study of environmental and organisational challenges. This dimension reflects the organization's knowledge in order to increase capacity and streamline learning processes. KM is a collection of processes that entails identifying, obtaining, producing, disseminating, retaining, and applying suitable knowledge to the organization's goals at the right time, by the right person.

Defensive strategy refers to actions taken to safeguard a market position from attempts to expand it. In contrast to the attacking aspect, he places a premium on cost-cutting and efficiency. Strategic orientation, forward-thinking, and long-term vision are all important aspects of the Perspective Strategy.

The ability of an organisation to adapt to changing environmental conditions is at the heart of strategic management concepts. Long-term vision is a strategic concern for survival in a competitive market when faced with environmental change.

In comparison to competitors, the Precursor Strategy is a step forward. After a strategic emphasis in pursuing new markets and goods, the pre-activation focuses on innovative behaviours. Market leadership is exhibited by companies that exhibit these competitive behaviours.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the dictionary, the word slim means "low fat." Toyota's production system, which decreases or eliminates drain concentration, is the source of lean production. After the Ford System was updated and renamed lean, Taiichi Ohno, a Toyota technical consultant, was engineered in 1950. In general, every type of manufacturing factor, such as materials, personnel, parts, equipment, and time, that exceeds the minimum required value and does not provide value added is wasted and should be eliminated, according to this approach.

The dictionary definition of agile is "fast and agile, as well as the capacity to think quickly and intelligently." In the Webster Dictionary, this word is alternatively translated as "Weaving and Warping." In 1991, Lee University performed research on thirteen large manufacturing companies, including GM, GE, and IBM, with the goal of determining what characteristics successful corporations had in 2006. There will be features. Following that, over 100 other organisations were investigated, and the findings of the aforementioned study were published in a book in 1995.

The concept of agility:

Adapting to changes (foreseen or unanticipated) in a timely and appropriate manner. Taking advantage of these shifts and turning them into opportunities (Zhang, 2000). In a study, Nicholas 1999 says that over the last decade, automotive firms have placed a greater emphasis on these approaches, which can help them gain a competitive advantage by establishing lean provider networks, collaborative partnerships, and supply chain management. In reality, major industrial companies have spent more than half of their financial resources on procuring raw materials and components, and this investment share has tended to reduce automotive companies' reliance on external sources. After the introduction of the models (H) in the field of supplier management and analysis, we attempted to do so in this study, comparing them to introduce strategic alliances and classification their strategic suppliers.

According to Turban et al. (2002), information technology coordinates intra-organizational operations, which are at the heart of supply chain management. Virtual Organizations and information systems integrate and combine product designable design with

production design and production processes, as well as the sort of information technology required for in-house and outsourcing coordination.

In your study, Bunker (2006) first defined the service supply chain operations, then built a framework based on hierarchical analysis to evaluate the supply chain's performance.

Supply Chain Management

By monitoring communications in industrial organisations, supply chain management maintains customer relationship management. In recent years, this field has become increasingly essential (si et al., 2011).

Supply chain management as part of company strategy has received little attention in the literature, and there are just a few studies that deal with strategic supply chain management in a peripheral way. Yeung (2008) believes that focusing on suppliers should be part of any corporate strategy, and finds a link between strategic supply management and both time and cost efficiency. Although Yeung emphasises supplier emphasis at the strategic level, we believe the scope of strategic supply chain management should be broader than that proposed in the previous study. As a result, strategic supply chain management comprises strategic focus, customer responsiveness, and supplier focus in the current study.

AIMS OF THE STUDY

To investigate the impact of company strategy on supply chain performance evaluation and measurement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Because there have been other studies in this subject, and there are also frameworks in the relationship between strategy and practise, the research approach was chosen based on the fact that this study is in terms of dealing with quantitative theory. This study is based on the purpose of applied research because it focuses on the development of applied knowledge in the field of strategic management. It is also based on how to obtain descriptive and descriptive data, as well as the type of correlation in which the relationship between variables is based on the research purpose of the analysis. This study's statistical population includes dairy industry units and business managers, as well as experts from dairy companies. The statistical population of this study was dairy companies. There are 29 dairy firms in the area. These businesses were all employed as research subjects. 25 The company was eventually chosen as a prime example based on the information received from these companies.

The Cronbach's alpha method was used to determine the test's reliability. The Cronbach Alpha of a questionnaire was calculated using the SPSS programme. It was 0.87, showing a high level of trustworthiness. The Cronbach's alpha was then calculated independently for each set of indices for structural model convergence.

Reliability

The Cronbach's alpha method was utilised to measure the questionnaire's reliability in this study. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is used to determine how one-dimensional attitudes, judgments,

beliefs, and other difficult-to-measure categories are. The purpose is to determine how far respondents have taken the same questions. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient is calculated using spectra or scales.

Table 1: Cronbach's alpha coefficient

Variables	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
Business Strategy	86%
Efficiency	87 %
Supply chain management	82%

DATA ANALYSIS

Frequency tests, charts, mean, and standard deviation are employed in the descriptive part. The regression test and the correlation test were employed to analyse the data. SPSS is the programme used. There is a Pearson association between supply networks and performance efficiency. There is a two-way link in correlation.

Table 2: Correlation between business strategy and measurement

Variables	Relationship rate	Sig
business strategy on performance efficiency and supply chains	0/76	0/000

The relationship between company strategy and performance review and supply chain efficiency measurement is 0 /76. The findings of the tests reveal that there is a positive and significant association between supply chains and business strategy and performance.

With a 95% confidence level, alignment with the business plan can considerably explain the difference in performance evaluation and supply chains at 1%. At a 95% confidence level, the subscale share of business strategy alignment (=0.76) is significant. The order of the values of the standard correlation coefficients is also shown by the values of the calculated separation correlation coefficients. As a result, alignment with business strategy affects supply chain performance evaluation and measurement, and a positive beta score implies a positive association between these two components, this hypothesis can be considered to be supported.

CONCLUSION

According to the findings of this study's analysis of assumptions, there is a disconnect between supply chain management dimensions (adaptability and changeability, position of power penetration, customer needs, and business strategy) and performance evaluation and chain metrics performance evaluation.

REFERENCES

Blumentritt, T. and Danis,W.M. (2006), "Business strategy types and innovative practices", Journal of Managerial Issues Vol.XVIII, No.2 (Summer), pp.274-291.

- Hajar, Ibnu. (2015). Effect of Business Strategy on Innovation and Firm Performance in the Small Industrial Sector .The International Journal Of Engineering And Science (IJES), 4(2),1-9.
- Miles, R.E. and Snow,C.C. (1978). Organizational Strategy, Structure, and Process, McGraw Hill,New York,NY.
- Oltra, M.J. and Flor, M.L.(2010). The moderating effect of business strategy on the relationship between operations strategy and firms results, International Journal of operations & production management,Vol.30 No.6,pp.612-638.
- Sirsath,V.R., Dalu, R.S.(2015). Supply Chain Performance Evaluation Models: A Study. International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology,2 (11),182-190.
- Shaharudin. M.R et al.(2018). A Content Analysis of Current Issues in Supply Chain Management. , 7 (5), 199-212
- Talavera, G.V.(2008).Understanding supply chain management and its applicability in the Philippines. Philippine Management Review,15,1-14.
- Tan, K. C. (2001). A framework of supply chain management literature. European Journal of Purchasing & Supply Management 7, 39-48.
- Thakkar J, K, A A, Deshmukh S. (2009). Supply chain performance measurement framework for small and medium scale enterprises. Benchmarking: An International Journal. 16 (5): 702--723.